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War Booty Bells

Three bells
rang in the old church

blessing the town:
clanging, and tolling
echoing the nearby towns

church goers are fervent to pray in the church
sand bricks on the walls hear their worship

the Americans came
brought their garrison
controlled the town

the locals in forced labor
and women were molested
triggered a surprise attack
white men defeated
bells were stolen.